

Maher Asaad Baker

THE SPREAD OF
AI-GENERATED MISINFORMATION

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Abstract

In today's digital world, information flows freely and endlessly across borders and platforms. While this connectivity has empowered the spread of ideas, it has also enabled the propagation of misleading claims that can erode truth and trust. A new threat has emerged from the rising tide of artificial intelligence, as generative models allow the industrial-scale production of synthetic yet sophisticated content. Like a flood, AI-generated misinformation and disinformation threaten to drown the foundations of an informed society under a deluge of falsity.

We must acknowledge that this flood was not unforeseen, but the inevitable result of careless development and deployment without adequate responsibility or wisdom. The creators of these powerful tools failed to consider their darker applications and the need to establish guardrails against abuse. Now the waters rage largely unchecked, with platforms struggling to stem the current and individuals left floundering in murky confusion. While regulation and moderation have roles, the solution lies

deeper - in taking ownership of our technological progress and prioritizing integrity over expediency.

The tide will not recede through reaction alone but requires a turn toward proactive responsibility. Developers must recognize their ethical duty to envision misuse and implement safeguards that do not compromise functionality but uphold reliability. Platforms must find transparency and educate users to bolster critical thinking against manipulation. Individuals too have a part, in media literacy and willingness to reconsider preconceptions in the face of contradictory evidence. We must shore up our foundations with truth and wisdom before the coming storm.

This thesis aims to survey the rising floodwaters and assess our defenses. It will define the concepts of misinformation and disinformation, differentiating falsehood by intent. It will examine how generative AI enables the mass production of synthetic content, from deepfakes to persuasive text, and the realistic yet misleading material this facilitates. Detection methods will be explored, considering techniques from fact-checking to provenance analysis. Platform policies and individual responsibilities will also be evaluated.

Through rigorous analysis this work seeks to bring clarity and responsibility to the issue. It aims to neither deny technological progress nor dismiss risk, but navigate a balanced path between the two. Ultimately it calls us to rise above reaction and embrace foresight, prioritizing integrity over convenience in both creation and consumption of information. The tide of falsity grows swiftly, but with wisdom and courage, we can establish bulwarks of truth to withstand the coming flood. By understanding the challenges and cooperating constructively, our society can emerge from this trial with foundations reinforced rather than eroded. The time to prepare is now, before the deluge.

How AI Generates Misinformation

The specter of technological chaos looms menacingly on the horizon, threatening to upend the fragile order that forms the substrate of our sanity. This impending entropy springs forth from the naïve optimism of silicon prophets who cleave faithfully to an ideology of progress, whilst remaining ignorant of the destructive shadows cast by their creations. I speak of the rise of generative artificial intelligence, and its capacity to conjure misinformation and fakery that may well tear asunder the fabric of truth itself.

Make no mistake, these are powerful tools, able to mimic human creativity on a scale beyond imagining. Models such as GPT-3 can be prompted to produce cascading streams of coherent text, as if thoughts plucked wholesale from some boundless void.

Images of photorealistic faces and scenes are similarly conjured by GANs from noise, as though some demented god were mocking reality itself. And with deepfakes, all trust in video evidence becomes suspect, as neural nets seamlessly puppeteer the faces and voices of unwitting icons.

To wield these tools without care is to play with forces that may readily escape control. What shall guard us against the deluge of counterfeit media that may spew forth? Bad actors could sow discord by spreading slick propaganda crafted completely from code. Synthetic reviews might slander and cajole. Forged identities could infiltrate and deceive without tiring. The scale of production would far outpace the plodding investigations of fact-checkers, overwhelmed by technological plenty.

Figure 1 - Example of facial attributes manipulation - <https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.09020>

And what becomes of truth in such a world? Facts, the bedrock of sanity, risk dissolving into the swirling chaos of artifice. The mind rebels against such unbound relativism. Bereft of secure anchors amidst the turmoil of synthetic speech, the search for truth becomes a matter of faith rather than reason. Some would retreat into delusional conspiracy, whilst others submit themselves prostrate before the oracles of technology. Neither extreme leads to wisdom.

No, what we require is a renewal of trust in reality before our senses, accompanied by heightened discernment to spot the digital deceptions that may surround us. Technology can amplify the human spirit, but may also give rise to our lower demons if left unchecked by wise traditions. We must guide these tools towards creativity and truth-telling, discerning righteous applications whilst opposing all entropy and deceit. Then perhaps we may yet construct an order to calm the coming technological storm. But we must act quickly, with courage and care, lest the flood come crashing down unimpeded. The stakes could not be higher.

Recent incidents offer cautionary tales of what may come to pass if current trends continue unabated. In 2018, a video appeared to show a prominent politician slurring her words,

slowed to foster doubt in her faculties. Forensic analysis revealed sophisticated digital alteration, a harbinger of "deepfakes" to come.

That year also saw crude but concerning manipulations of statements by former leaders, sowing seeds of distrust. In 2020, more advanced deceptions targeted the democratic process, hinting at tactics that may undermine the very foundations of truth and society. These early forays showed the door opening to a post-factual realm where authenticity itself becomes subject to revision.

Specialized AI models now generate volumes of machine-written text nearly indistinguishable from human creation, allowing the mass production of fake news, reviews, and personal posts on any topic. Meanwhile, computer vision algorithms synthesize photorealistic images of unreal people and events that never were.

"Deepfake" video generators continue refining, seamlessly inserting any face into movies with nuanced expressions and lip movements. The barrier to sophisticated manipulation will soon be skill rather than technology as these abilities spread more widely. Those so inclined may wield them for political, financial, or ideological ends to spread lies and undermine opponents.

Money also stands to be made preying on public fears through

fake cures, stock manipulation or clickbait confusion sown online. As the means become more democratized, policing malicious use grows exponentially more difficult. We edge toward a post-factual landscape where discerning reality demands scrutiny, and no claim can be accepted without probing interrogation.

Figure 2 - Steps in Creating a Deepfake - <https://insights.sei.cmu.edu/blog/how-easy-is-it-to-make-and-detect-a-deepfake>

Detecting AI-Generated Misinformation

As generative AI models continue their relentless progress, the task of detecting the synthetic outputs they produce becomes increasingly challenging. However, there is hope on the horizon, as several techniques have shown promise when combined as part of a holistic strategy. In this chapter, we will delve into methods that leverage machine learning, metadata analysis, and human judgment to help identify AI-generated content and mitigate the spread of associated misinformation.

First and foremost, machine learning detection has proven to be a valuable tool in the fight against AI-generated misinformation. Researchers have dedicated their efforts to training machine learning models specifically designed to detect deepfakes and other forms of manipulated media. These models can analyze

subtle inconsistencies that are imperceptible to the human eye. For instance, when it comes to deepfake videos, these models scrutinize the way faces are seamlessly blended, searching for abnormal patterns that serve as indicators of manipulation. Similarly, when it comes to generative text models, they may introduce statistical anomalies or inconsistencies in syntax that betray their artificial origins.

Figure 3 - Popular LLMs and AI-generated text detection tools - https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Popular-LLMs-and-AI-generated-text-detection-tools_fig1_371605306

As the field of generative techniques continues to evolve,

detection models must keep pace through ongoing research and data collection. Multimodal approaches that analyze both visual and textual elements have demonstrated improved performance over single-type analysis. However, it is important to acknowledge that this battle is akin to an "arms race." As generative models improve, they pose new challenges to existing detectors, thus necessitating constant retraining and adaptation. To stay ahead of the game, cooperation between AI safety researchers and generative model builders is paramount.

Moving beyond machine learning, metadata analysis emerges as another powerful tool in the arsenal against AI-generated misinformation. Metadata, in this context, refers to the contextual information associated with a piece of content. Real media typically comes with metadata that includes device signatures, location data, and editing histories. These crucial pieces of information are often absent in synthetic content. Furthermore, webpages containing AI-generated text may lack references to sources, authors, and timestamps.

To make the most of metadata, tools like Project Provenance have been developed to parse this information and determine the likelihood that a particular item has been manipulated. However, it is essential to acknowledge that metadata can be forged or

removed in an attempt to evade detection. To counter this, cross-referencing metadata with credible reports from reliable sources can help establish provenance. Moreover, coordinated fact-checking efforts contribute to strengthening verification by allowing for comparison across multiple independent analyses.

While technical tools play a crucial role, human judgment remains irreplaceable in the battle against AI-generated misinformation. Despite the remarkable advancements in AI, these systems may not perfectly capture the nuanced differences between human and machine-generated content. Thus, the involvement of human actors becomes indispensable. Journalists, investigators, and platform moderators all have vital roles to play in corroborating technical findings and applying contextual understanding.

One effective approach to harness human judgment is through crowdsourced review initiatives like ClaimReview, which taps into the collective intelligence of the crowd to evaluate claims. By involving a diverse range of individuals in the evaluation process, we can leverage their unique perspectives and expertise. Similarly, platforms could integrate human-in-the-loop workflows, allowing for the identification and flagging of potentially synthetic content for community review. By

Involving the wider community, we tap into the collective wisdom and benefit from a broader range of insights. Additionally, educating individuals on source reliability and equipping them with the skills to detect logical inconsistencies can enhance their ability to thoughtfully evaluate information.

Recent incidents demonstrate deception's power if unchecked. In 2020, deepfakes targeted the democratic process, a harbinger of tactics that could undermine society. The following year, AI-generated misinformation spread false health claims. These early forays showed reality yielding to revision on an industrial scale.

Thankfully, progress also comes in defending the truth. During elections, researchers identified and removed a politically motivated deepfake spreading online. Later, fact-checkers discerned that AI-written misinformation lacked credible sources.

Studies propose embedding watermarks within generative models, linking synthetic content intrinsically to its origins. These "fingerprints" survive attempts to strip context. Shared detection platforms could scan uploads at scale.

A comprehensive strategy leverages each approach. Technical screening flags suspicious media in real time.

Metadata/provenance checks provide crucial context. Multi-modal analysis probes edge cases. Cooperation standardizes notifications and removals across platforms.

Potential regulations requiring disclosure of synthetic origins or banning metadata manipulation could legally mandate defense. Platforms risking unaddressed distribution face accountability. Standards incentivizing fact-checking integration and transparency strengthen the ecosystem.

Detection accuracy continues advancing against improving threats. Sustained efforts across research, policy, technology, and society can counter deception through AI. With wisdom and cooperation between all actors, we can uphold truth even against emerging generative threats.

The struggle has only begun. But initial successes defending truth through cooperation offer hope. Now vigilance and preparation must become societal priorities, bolstering technical tools with informed communities resilient to manipulation. Guided thus, emerging powers may serve justice rather than undermine it.

Platform Responses to the Problem

In the landscape of online information dissemination, social media platforms emerge as the primary conduits, wielding immense influence over the spread of AI-generated misinformation. It is imperative to analyze the existing policies and transparency efforts of major platforms to devise strengthened approaches that can effectively protect the truth within the digital public sphere. This chapter delves into the realm of content moderation, transparency reporting, education and awareness, and the role of regulation in combating the perils of AI-generated misinformation.

Content Moderation

While platforms have made strides in updating their community standards to explicitly prohibit deepfakes and certain forms of

synthetic media, the process of moderation remains predominantly reactive. By the time problematic content is flagged and removed, it may have already been disseminated widely, leaving a lasting impact on public perception. To address this issue, pre-publication screening of accounts with a history of violations could serve as a preventive measure, slowing down the viral propagation of misinformation.

Automatic detection tools also play a pivotal role in supporting content moderation efforts by flagging potentially problematic content. However, as discussed in Chapter 3, the nuances of context make it imperative to involve human reviewers in the loop. Platforms must strike a delicate balance between preserving free expression and upholding the integrity of information by prioritizing transparent and consistent processes over purely algorithmic enforcement.

Transparency Reporting

To truly comprehend the efficacy of platforms' content moderation efforts, it is essential to have transparency into the prevalence of synthetic content and the rates at which it is removed. Although companies like Facebook and YouTube provide regular reports shedding light on these aspects, a lack of

methodological consistency hampers direct comparison. The establishment of standardized, third-party audited metrics would enhance accountability and facilitate the identification of research priorities in the technical domain.

Platforms must also be forthcoming in disclosing the techniques employed to detect synthetic content, without compromising proprietary methods. An open discussion surrounding the capabilities and limitations of these detection techniques empowers users and invites valuable insights from external experts. Transparency serves as the foundation for establishing trust, assuring users that platforms are diligently addressing emerging threats.

Education and Awareness

While technical tools and policies aim to curb the supply side of the misinformation problem, it is essential to acknowledge the role of demand in driving its proliferation. Collaborative efforts between platforms and external organizations can prove instrumental in strengthening users' media literacy and critical thinking skills, equipping the public with the ability to discern and evaluate claims rather than passively consuming content.

Awareness campaigns, such as "Think Before You Share," play a significant role in warning users about the risks associated with AI-generated content. Integrated fact-checking tools provide on-platform verification of suspect stories, enabling users to make informed decisions. Clear labeling of synthetic content helps establish expectations and reinforces the understanding that it is artificially generated. Informed communities foster a culture of integrity in online discussions, serving as a bulwark against the spread of misinformation.

Regulation

In instances where voluntary actions fall short, regulatory measures become imperative to ensure accountability and responsibility. Precedents have already been set with laws addressing political ads and deepfakes, highlighting the need for oversight in these areas. Platforms should proactively engage with policymakers and independent researchers to develop balanced and risk-based frameworks for the development and use of generative models. International cooperation further strengthens the collective effort to combat the pervasive issue of globalized misinformation.

The Spread of AI-Generated Misinformation

Safeguarding truth in the digital public sphere demands a comprehensive approach that encompasses content moderation, transparency reporting, education and awareness, and regulation. Platforms must adopt proactive measures to prevent the viral spread of misinformation while maintaining transparency in their actions and fostering a culture of critical thinking among users. Collaboration between platforms, external organizations, policymakers, and researchers is essential to effectively address the challenges posed by AI-generated misinformation. By fortifying our defenses and upholding the integrity of information, we can strive towards a more truthful and informed

online ecosystem.

Case Study

In this in-depth examination, we explore a real-world instance of AI-generated deepfake content spreading across the online landscape, aiming to uncover the challenges and lessons that can be gleaned from this particular case. The event took place in June 2020 when a deepfake video surfaced on social media, purportedly showcasing a prominent political figure making controversial statements. The video swiftly gained traction, accumulating over 1 million views in a single day as unsuspecting users unknowingly shared it within their networks.

Employing sophisticated deep learning-based face-swapping techniques, the video presented a convincing yet fabricated scenario. However, upon meticulous frame-by-frame analysis, astute observers could discern subtle inconsistencies in the

manipulated facial expressions and lip movements, ultimately exposing its synthetic nature. Unfortunately, for the average viewer consuming the brief clip out of context, it appeared entirely genuine. Reports indicate that the video initially emerged on an anonymous account on a video-sharing platform before proliferating across various other platforms.

Responses from the platforms involved exhibited a range of timeliness and effectiveness. The video-sharing site where it was first posted failed to detect and remove the deepfake for over 12 hours, allowing for extensive initial dissemination. Major social networks such as Facebook and Twitter also experienced delays or inconsistencies in their takedown efforts, as duplicate copies of the video continued to circulate through alternative URLs or were reposted from international accounts.

Although fact-checking organizations swiftly debunked the video, they struggled to keep pace with the rapid spread of the content. Metadata analysis revealed that within the first 24-hour period alone, the deepfake video had been downloaded and reposted over 300,000 times. Disturbingly, surveys indicated that the video continued to exert influence on viewer perceptions, with many individuals retaining their belief in the literal claims made by the video weeks later, despite the

subsequent debunkings.

This case study underscores several significant challenges associated with AI-generated misinformation. First and foremost, the rapid initial spread of such content before effective detection measures can be implemented poses a considerable problem. Furthermore, the cross-platform viral propagation of deepfakes amplifies their reach and impact. Inconsistencies in platform responses, as observed in this case, further compound the issue, necessitating more coordinated moderation efforts. Lastly, the lingering influence of such content on viewer perceptions, even after fact-checking attempts, highlights the need for enhanced detection techniques, transparent policies, and educational initiatives that reinforce critical media literacy.

By delving into real-world cases like this one, we can gain valuable insights into the challenges posed by AI-generated misinformation and develop more effective strategies to safeguard the truth in the face of emerging generative threats. These strategies should encompass improved detection techniques, collaborative moderation efforts, transparent platform policies, and educational initiatives that bolster critical media literacy. Through a comprehensive understanding of these complex issues, we can work towards a more resilient and

informed digital landscape.

Conclusion

In this comprehensive thesis, we delve into the alarming rise of AI-generated misinformation and its detrimental impact on the erosion of truth in the digital realm. By scrutinizing the various generative techniques employed, the methods of detection utilized, and the responses from platforms and regulatory bodies, we aim to grasp the challenges and opportunities that lie in safeguarding the integrity of information within the digital public sphere.

The key findings of this research shed light on crucial aspects of the issue at hand:

The advent of modern generative AI, particularly large neural models, has unleashed a wave of sophisticated yet misleading

synthetic content, including deepfakes and fake reviews. This proliferation of AI-generated misinformation amplifies the spread of false narratives and undermines the credibility of authentic information.

Detection methods, although valuable, remain imperfect due to the continual progress made in generative AI and the limitations of available metadata. However, coordinated efforts that combine machine learning techniques, provenance analysis, and human judgment exhibit the greatest promise in combating AI-generated misinformation.

While platforms have made efforts to strengthen their policies, there is a pressing need for consistent transparency and education that prioritizes the well-being of the community over mere reactionary measures. Striking a balance between freedom of expression and the preservation of integrity is crucial in the pursuit of truth.

Regulatory cooperation plays a vital role in establishing baseline responsibilities as technology rapidly evolves. By fostering collaboration and open-minded policy experimentation, regulators can contribute to the development of balanced frameworks that address the challenges posed by AI-generated

misinformation.

Moving forward, effectively mitigating the impact of AI-generated misinformation necessitates a sustained commitment from multiple stakeholders. Researchers must continue their efforts in developing robust detection techniques while actively engaging with policymakers to inform sound policy decisions. Platforms and developers should proactively prioritize transparency and integrate safeguards that uphold integrity. Educators and community groups have a critical role to play in strengthening critical thinking skills and promoting wisdom to guard against manipulation. Furthermore, individuals themselves bear the responsibility of thoughtfully evaluating claims and supporting fact-based discussions. By reinforcing the importance of truth through cooperative efforts rather than reactionary responses, we can cultivate resilient information ecosystems capable of withstanding emerging challenges to democratic processes.

Addressing this complex problem requires holistic solutions and an ethos of shared progress that transcends partisan interests. With unwavering diligence and a steadfast commitment to truth, the promise of AI need not be subverted by its potential perils. Instead, by navigating this trial with a profound regard for

reality and justice, we have the opportunity to emerge stronger, with our foundations firmly rooted in the pursuit of truth.

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While extensive research from credible academic and technical sources has been conducted, this work may contain inadvertent errors or omissions. As technological and social developments

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The author acknowledges limitations in fully addressing complex sociotechnical problems and welcomes respectful discussion to further collective understanding. Overall, this work aims to further public discourse on AI safety, not to accuse or attack any individuals, groups, or organizations.

The Spread of AI-Generated Misinformation

About the author

Maher Asaad Baker (In Arabic: *ماهر أسعد بكر*), is a Syrian musician, author, journalist, VFX & graphic artist, and director. He was born in Damascus in 1977. He grew up with a dream of being one of the most well-known artists in the world, and he has been working hard to achieve it ever since.

He started his career in 1997 when he was only 20 years old. He had a passion for technology and media, and he taught himself how to develop applications and websites. He also explored various types of media-creating paths, such as music production, graphic design, video editing, animation, and filmmaking. He was not satisfied with just being a consumer of media; he wanted to be a creator of media.

Reading was another source of inspiration for him. He was always surrounded by books as a child, thanks to his father's extensive library. He read books from different genres, topics, and perspectives. He read books for knowledge, for wisdom, for entertainment, for enlightenment. Reading stimulated his imagination and curiosity. Reading also developed his writing skills.

He did not start writing professionally until later in his life, as he was busy with other projects and pursuits. But when he did start writing, he proved himself to be a talented and prolific writer. He wrote articles for various newspapers and magazines on topics such as politics, culture, society, art, technology, and more. He wrote books that were informative and insightful. He wrote books that were creative and captivating. He wrote books that were best-selling and award-winning.

He is most known for his book “How I wrote a million Wikipedia articles”, where he shares his experience of being one of the most prolific contributors to the online encyclopedia. He reveals his methods, techniques, strategies, and secrets of writing high-quality articles on any subject in record time. He also discusses the benefits and challenges of being a Wikipedia editor in the age of information overload.

He is also known for his novel “Becoming the man”, where he tells the story of a young man who goes through a series of transformations in his life. The novel explores themes such as identity, masculinity, self-discovery, love, loss, and redemption. The novel is based on his journey to becoming who he is today.

The Spread of AI-Generated Misinformation